

IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICINE

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Abstract: Currently, medicine, like all fields, is developing. This article talks about the prospects of modern medicine, the development of new works.

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As we all know that today's world is full of modern technological devices and gadgets. Almost everything technology is used. Today is an era of technology. Technology plays a very important role in the healthcare industry. There are a lot of machines, devices and gadgets invented to improve the healthcare of the people. With the help of modern technological gadgets and devices, the treatment of the patients can be done effectively. There are a lot of benefits of technology for the health care of people from different aspects. With the help of modern technology, people can easily find doctors and hospitals in case of emergency, and can easily contact them. Technology is very helpful in saving the life of people. Technology is advancing day by day and improving the healthcare of people around the world. Now I am going to discuss all the reasons by which we can say why modern technology is important in the healthcare of the people. One of the benefits of technology in healthcare is, that doctors can save real-time records of their patients. Before the technology, it was very difficult for doctors to analyze their patients' health status. That how much their patients' health improves and how to treat their next treatment. They forgot their patient's previous treatment history. Technology improves the health analysis of the patients, with the help of modern technology doctors can easily analyze their patients' health and diseases. Before the advancement in medical technology doctors only predicted diseases by the symptoms from which patients were suffering. Which was not an effective way of analyzing the patients' health. Sometimes the prediction was wrong. Which was very harmful to the health of the patients. But now thanks to modern technology medical gadgets and devices, which can easily analyze the patients' health and identify the exact diseases, from which patients suffering. I think this is one of the most beneficial effects of modern technology in healthcare. This proves the importance of modern technology in healthcare.

With the help of modern technology, doctors can easily and on time treat patients. Modern technology helps patients to contact the doctor in the case of an emergency. Without wasting time or delay doctors can easily approach patients in an emergency and save their life. With the help of modern technology, patients can easily make connections and communicate with their doctors from anywhere. They can update the doctors about their healthcare conditions and improvements. then the doctors can suggest them the treatments for their health, and their health care improves. New invention and advancements in modern technology for healthcare is wearable technology. Patients wear it, and it analyzes their body condition. It seems better Nah, all the things for your healthcare are in your hand. Now at any time you can analyze your body health condition, and take care of your health. Modern technology makes it

very simple and easy for people to take care of their health, this is how much modern technology is important for your healthcare. Artificial organs or we can say human-made organs are the most shocking wonder of modern technology. Many artificial organs are made to save human lives. Bones, joints, artificial hands, artificial feet, artificial hearts, and many more are made for human health. Many people we can see in our society, live happily with artificial organs in their bodies. It reduces the disabilities of the people and makes them able to live happily. Modern technology saves time in the health care of the people. Before the technology, it took a lot of time in curing patients' health. Because there was no such technology for analyzing the patients' health conditions and giving them proper treatments. But now with the help of modern technology, within seconds doctors can identify the disease and cure their health. One of the benefits of modern technology in the health care of people is online treatment support.

With the help of modern technology, people can easily contact doctors, hospitals, and experts online and took treatment from them and take care of their health. Many hail the wave of technological progress as Mankind's greatest gift to himself. Indeed, the pervasive nature of technology has permeated every stratum of our society, and the healthcare field is no exception. The advent of technology has revolutionized the healthcare industry in multifarious ways, and this blog will discuss various aspects of how this modernizing wave has benefitted the healthcare field. Here are the 5 key benefits of leveraging technology in healthcare:

1. Easy access to patient medical records
2. Reduction in medical errors
3. Greater patient care
4. Improved patient education

1. Easy access to patient medical records

The collection of patients' data is one of the most paramount aspects in the healthcare field. Medical data is essential for doctors to analyze the patient's situation and illness and then to find a possible cure for it. In the past, patient records used to create large amounts of paperwork because everything was on paper and pen. Accessing past records was troublesome. However, with the advent of digitalisation, the medical information of patients can be keyed into a cloud-based, digitized system. This has provided extraordinary ease for specialists, patients, and medical billers to access with a click of a button, from anywhere at anytime.

This system is called Electronic Medical Records (EMRs), or Electronic Health Records (EHRs). It is a collection of patient and population health information electronically stored in a digital format. Sameer Bhargava, who serves as the chief information officer and chief technology officer at Caregiver, Inc., emphasized the much-needed efficiencies EHRs had provided them with. Across an eight-month period, his team migrated eight million records from paper to an EHR system. "Moving to electronic records elevates our care ecosystem into a cohesive process that can provide a better network of services," Bhargava says. Therefore, technology has simplified the collection of medical records, enabling providers to mine out patients' information in a matter of minutes.

2. Reduction in medical errors

Medical errors are an increasing public concern as they are repeated constantly and are inevitable parts of the results of human performance. According to official Starfield, and the

American Institute of Medicine (IOM), medical errors in U.S. hospitals and healthcare institutions are the third leading cause of death and nearly 98,000 annual deaths occur due to medical errors in hospitals.

Fortunately, technology has facilitated the development of systems that are proven to reduce medical errors and save more lives. The clinical Decision Support (CDS) system provides the health care professional with medical information and patient-specific information. This information is rationally filtered and presented to the healthcare professional at appropriate times, intending to enhance the decision-making of the healthcare provider. It is capable of providing evidence-based standards and guidance; procedures and protocols; rules and recommendations for care, etc. A study done by RA. Miller and colleagues showed that the CDS system reduces serious medication errors by 55% and total medication errors by 83%, highlighting the transcendent power of such a system to aid healthcare professionals in their diagnosis.

3. Greater patient care

The use of technology can increase patient engagement, providing insight to help create hyper-targeted, personalized health and wellness plans. Devices in the form of wearables like fitness bands and other wirelessly connected devices like Fitbits can monitor one's blood pressure and Electrocardiograph (ECG), giving patients and specialists access to personalized information. These devices can depict calorie count, exercise checks, appointments, blood pressure variations, etc.

Specialists can keep track of patients' health more efficaciously, such as their adherence to treatment plans, etc. This is especially pertinent for elderly patients and those living alone, where their family members or concerned healthcare providers will be promptly alerted if any abnormality is detected. As such, such technological gadgets ensure that patients enjoy superlative care, enhancing the healthcare experience and quality for all.

4. Improved patient education

Patient education takes on an imperative role in healthcare, and specialists are embracing technologies that can help better inform and engage patients. According to the results of a recent survey of 200 U.S. physicians conducted by PatientPoint and Digital Health Coalition, more than 75% of physicians believe that leveraging patient education and engagement technology can help improve the patient experience. 95% of respondents also reported that they were currently using engagement technology tools to educate and engage with patients.

Technology has provided softwares and applications that present customized health education information to patients based on their specific needs and conditions. For example, the Patient Electronic Portal is a secure online application that provides patients access to their personal health information and 2-way electronic communication with their care provider using a computer or a mobile device. A study has found that this application has increased patients' compliance to preventive medical precautions, their medical adherence, and self-awareness and management of their diseases.

Conclusion

In the scheme of things, technology has indeed revolutionized the healthcare industry, with many systems and softwares available that you can consider utilising to streamline your logistics and workflow, and at the same time provide superlative care to your patients.

We do hope you find this article informative and useful for your practice. If you are looking to elevate your medical practices to the next level, UNO Clinic Management System is always ready to assist you.

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